

Closed-Form Cognate Algorithm with Closure Parameter for Real-Time Path-Generation of Four-Bar Linkages

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Abstract

The existence of two distinct configurations in a Grashof four-bar mechanism required introducing a tenth configuration parameter into the conventional nine-parameter model. In this study, closed-form kinematic equations are derived to clearly differentiate these configurations and to describe the motion of three Roberts–Chebyshev cognate mechanisms. Using these formulations, the simultaneous operation of all three cognates was simulated, and the results were validated against manually fabricated prototype mechanisms.

The verified cognate algorithm was then integrated with the General Coupler Curve Equation (GCCE) to develop the Real-Time Interactive Cognate Path Synthesis (RICPS) method, which provides an interactive and easily accessible platform for mechanism synthesis. RICPS enables the concurrent visualization of three operating cognate mechanisms corresponding to a coupler curve that passes through user-defined precision points. The performance of the proposed method was compared with results reported in the literature, and the effectiveness of the GCCE was evaluated for both Grashof and non-Grashof mechanisms.

Keywords: Cognate mechanisms; Four-bar linkage; Kinematic synthesis; Path generation; General Coupler Curve Equation; Path synthesis

1 Introduction

In mechanism design, cognate mechanisms are distinct linkages that generate an identical coupler curve [1]. They play a significant role by expanding the designer's range of alternatives and enhancing optimization processes [2, 3]. The Roberts–Chebyshev theorem provides the theoretical foundation for the study of four-bar cognate mechanisms and has guided extensive research in this field. According to this theorem, three different four-bar mechanisms can be constructed to trace the same coupler curve [4]. Cognate mechanisms thus offer valuable design flexibility through variations in link lengths, geometric layouts, and kinematic characteristics [5].

In both synthesis and analysis, cognate mechanisms not only provide alternative designs but also serve as a robust tool for verifying the accuracy of synthesis results [6]. The availability of multiple mechanisms capable of generating the same coupler curve supports design validation and refinement processes [7, 8]. Their advantages are particularly evident in applications such as dynamic balancing, precision mechanism design, and multi-generation systems [9].

The coupler curve of a four-bar mechanism defines the trajectory traced by its coupler point and plays a fundamental role in kinematic analysis [10]. Its mathematical representation provides a solid foundation for investigating the motion characteristics of the linkage [11]. Typically, the coupler curve is expressed through algebraic formulations or numerical analysis, enabling the computation of the mechanism's position, velocity, and acceleration parameters [12].

Kinematic synthesis of four-bar linkages involves determining the link lengths, angular parameters, and other geometric variables required to produce a specified coupler curve [13]. In this process, both analytical formulations and optimization techniques are employed to achieve the desired motion [14]. Accurate analytical modeling of the coupler curve is therefore essential for optimizing mechanism performance and ensuring precise task execution [15].

Numerous studies have focused on the analysis and synthesis of coupler curves. The Atlas of Coupler Curves by Hrones and Nelson (1951) provided a comprehensive reference for exploring the geometric properties of these curves [16]. Freudenstein and Roth (1963) advanced analytical methods in this field by introducing a third-order polynomial representation of the coupler curve [14]. More recently, Fourier series have been employed to represent coupler curves with complex geometries [17], and Wang et al. (2022) further enhanced this approach by developing models that improve its accuracy [18].

Research on cognate mechanisms has introduced innovative approaches to the mechanism design process. The Roberts–Chebyshev theorem enabled the systematic analysis of mechanisms capable of generating the same coupler curve, facilitating applications in static balancing, linear motion generation, and precision dwell mechanisms [19, 20]. Furthermore, cognate mechanisms provide a valuable foundation for enhancing optimization algorithms and expanding the range of available design alternatives [5].

In recent years, numerical methods and optimization algorithms have been increasingly applied to the analysis and synthesis of coupler curves. In particular, meta-heuristic techniques such as genetic algorithms, particle swarm optimization (PSO), and differential evolution have been employed to achieve optimal representations of the coupler curve. Yin et al. demonstrated that a variant of the teaching–learning-based optimization (TLBO) algorithm can effectively be used for the path-generation synthesis of four-bar mechanisms, illustrating the versatility of meta-heuristic methods in mechanism design [5]. Moreover, Bertini software and homotopy continuation techniques play a key role in solving the algebraic systems associated with coupler-curve equations. When combined with analytical formulations, these approaches both accelerate the design process and improve solution accuracy [21, 22].

The capability of four-bar mechanisms to operate under multiple configurations (e.g., distinct assembly closures) makes selecting the appropriate solution during path synthesis a critical challenge [23]. Several studies have reported that the distinction among alternative solutions to closed-loop equations is often overlooked, which may result in incorrect or infeasible mechanisms [10, 24, 25]. Therefore, the explicit inclusion of the configuration parameter within path-synthesis algorithms has been emphasized as a crucial step toward ensuring reliable and physically consistent results.

Finding a four-bar mechanism and a coupler point that together trace a prescribed path has long been a challenging problem. In most cases, no simple analytical equation can be fitted to a curve that is often sketched freehand by a designer, while the general equation of a coupler curve is too cumbersome to manipulate into the form of any desired trajectory. Additional difficulties arise from the improper placement of pivots, disproportionate link dimensions, unfavorable transmission angles, and the practical issue of whether the mechanism can be driven directly by a continuously rotating shaft. The transmission angle, in particular, has long been recognized as a critical performance criterion in mechanism design. Helmut Alt (1932) formulated the initial crank angle of a crank–rocker mechanism such that the deviation of the transmission angle from 90° is minimized [26]. Owing to the extensive arithmetic involved, the VDI (Verein Deutscher Ingenieure) later published this solution in the form of design charts. Designers typically prefer not to be limited to a single configuration but rather to have a family of feasible alternatives from which to choose [27].

A remarkably elegant insight into this long-standing problem was provided independently by Roberts and Chebyshev, who demonstrated that any given four-bar mechanism possesses two additional cognate linkages capable of generating the same coupler curve. This classical result stems from the observation that opposite links in a parallelogram-type mechanism undergo identical motion. For instance, Evans’s Grasshopper mechanism is a cognate of Watt’s approximate straight-line tracer, and Hoeken’s linkage is a cognate of Chebyshev’s straight-line mechanism. These examples naturally raise the question of whether there exist other, as-yet-undiscovered cognate mechanisms—beyond those described by Roberts and Chebyshev—that could provide designers with additional viable alternatives. The present study addresses this question by introducing a ten-parameter representation of the coupler curve of a four-bar linkage and by exploring all possible variations that interpolate a common set of precision points. However, the investigation revealed no new cognates beyond those already established by Roberts and Chebyshev.

Although the existence of three cognate mechanisms capable of tracing the same path is well established through the Roberts–Chebyshev theorem, the explicit computation and practical incorporation of these alternatives into design have often been overlooked or confined to cumbersome algebraic derivations in most studies [3, 8, 25]. In contrast, deriving cognate solutions directly from closed-form equations allows designers to rapidly evaluate multiple options, thereby greatly facilitating the synthesis process [8].

However, many existing methods are neither real-time nor interactive, and they typically require extensive computation times. The literature consistently notes that optimization-based approaches may involve hundreds or even thousands of iterations, while polynomial-based methods often become impractical due to the complexity of high-order systems [11, 12, 21]. These limitations clearly highlight the need for real-time, responsive, and user-friendly tools for practicing engineers. Moreover, the dependence of path synthesis on advanced algebraic manipulations and numerical algorithms continues to restrict its accessibility to non-specialist users [8, 10–12, 21, 24, 28, 29]. In this context, easily accessible software with a straightforward interface that requires no specialized expertise would directly address long-recognized gaps in literature.

To meet this need, the present study develops a real-time and easily accessible path synthesis method. First, a cognate algorithm is formulated to model configuration distinctions, and its simulation is implemented. Subsequently, a real-time, interactive curve-fitting framework is established using the Desmos Geometry platform. We refer to the proposed approach as Real-Time Interactive Cognate Path Synthesis (RICPS). With RICPS, designers can manually drag the desired precision points through which the coupler must pass and instantly observe the simultaneous motion of all three cognate mechanisms.

The contributions of this study can be summarized as follows:

- A ten-parameter coupler-curve formulation explicitly modeling configuration dependence for Grashof mechanisms has been developed. The closure parameter is not used solely for classification purposes but is directly integrated into the rocker and coupler angle equations in closed form.
- Starting from a reference four-bar mechanism, all primary and auxiliary parameters of the two Roberts–Chebyshev cognates are derived entirely in closed-form expressions. Thus, the cognate mechanisms are systematically expressed within a unified parametric framework.

- Through systematic exploration of the ten-parameter model space, it is confirmed that no additional cognate mechanisms exist beyond the Roberts–Chebyshev theorem. This result demonstrates that the cognate triple forms an algebraically closed structure within the adopted formulation.
- The parameter-dependent General Coupler Curve Equation (GCCE) is integrated into the precision-point fitting procedure, enabling direct closed-form cognate generation.
- This theoretical framework is transformed into a real-time and interactive synthesis workflow termed Real-Time Interactive Cognate Path Synthesis (RICPS).

2 Calculations and Simulation for a Single Mechanism

2.1 Naming and Orienting the Parameters of a Single Mechanism

The parameters of the mechanism illustrated in Fig. 1 are defined according to the following conventions.

In a single four-bar mechanism, two rotating links are connected to two fixed pivots: the input and output links. The shorter rotating link (input) is denoted by k , and the longer one (output) by K . If both links are of equal length, either label may be assigned arbitrarily. In summary, a four-bar mechanism can be regarded as consisting of two parts: an input section represented by lowercase letters and an output section represented by uppercase letters.

- The coordinates of the pivot point for the link of length k are denoted by (a,b) , and those for K by (A,B) .
- The length from the tip of k to the coupler point (CP) is denoted by d , and from K to the CP by D .
- The ground link (g) and the coupler link (c) retain their definitions and do not change.
- All direction references are consistently taken from k to K . For example, the direction of g is from (a,b) to (A,B) , and the direction of c is from the endpoint of k to the endpoint of K .
- The directions of d and D are always toward the coupler point (CP).
- All angles are measured counterclockwise, which is taken as the positive direction.

Traditionally, the coupler curve of a four-bar linkage is described using nine fundamental parameters. In this study, we adopt a ten-parameter formulation by incorporating the closure parameter introduced by Erbaş and Bayseç [30]. The closure parameter is determined according to the following sign convention:

Fig.1: Directed parameters of a four-bar linkage. (a) Orientation of the links and associated angles in the coupler-curve mechanism. (b) Vectors representing the coupler point (CP) and the directed angles..

2.2 Introducing the Tenth Parameter: Closure Parameter

Traditionally, a four-bar linkage is characterized by nine parameters. This description is sufficient for non-Grashof systems; however, for linkages that satisfy the Grashof condition, both the motion and the coupler curve depend on ten fundamental parameters. The additional parameter, termed the closure parameter by Erbaş and Bayseç [30], is defined in detail below.

When the nine conventional parameters are specified and the links are fabricated, the mechanism can be assembled in two distinct configurations: the open and the crossed forms, as illustrated in Fig. 2. In a Grashof linkage, it is not possible to transition from the open configuration (Fig. 2a) to the crossed configuration (Fig. 2b) during motion. By contrast, in non-Grashof linkages, both closures can be attained in a single motion because the rocker link is able to swing to the opposite side of the ground link. Consequently, for a Grashof linkage, it is essential to designate the intended operating configuration.

If a Grashof linkage is assembled as in Fig. 2a, it generates a coupler curve that differs from the one obtained when assembled as in Fig. 2b. In a non-Grashof linkage, however, the assembly configuration is immaterial, since both positions are naturally encountered during motion. In summary, Grashof linkages require an additional tenth parameter to specify the operating configuration, whereas nine parameters are sufficient to define the coupler curve of a non-Grashof linkage.

Grashof linkages are further classified as crank–rocker (CR), crank–crank (CC), or rocker–rocker (RR). The signs of the convex angles between the input and output links and the ground can be used as identifiers. In a Grashof RR system, both links retain the same angle sign. In a CR system, the sign of the convex angle between the crank and the ground remains constant throughout the

motion (Fig. 3). In a CC system, however, both links are capable of full rotation, rendering this definition invalid. In such cases, the direction of the input link's angle when the output link is aligned with the ground (zero ground angle) can instead serve as the distinguishing criterion (Fig. 3d).

Fig.2: Assembly of a four-bar linkage satisfying the Grashof condition. (a) Component parts of the linkage. (b) Configuration with input and output links on the same side (open configuration). (c) Configuration with input and output links on opposite sides (crossed configuration).

The most general definition applicable to all types of Grashof linkages is given as follows:

Closure parameter (s): This parameter specifies the configuration of a Grashof linkage and takes the value $+1$ for the convex (open) case or -1 for the crossed (diagonal) case. To assign its sign, the directional angle of the input link k relative to the ground is considered when the output link K is positioned at its minimum possible ground angle. If the linkage includes a rocker, the rocker is fixed at its minimum ground angle so that the crank and coupler are nearly colinear (Fig. 3a–b). If the linkage does not include a rocker (e.g., crank–crank systems), the output link K is held at zero angle with respect to the ground, representing its minimum position. Under these conditions, two distinct closures exist depending on whether the ground angle of the input link k is positive or negative. A positive convex configuration corresponds to $s=+1$, whereas a negative crossed configuration corresponds to $s=-1$.

Fig.3: a) Open configuration for a crank-rocker or double rocker system b) crossed configuration for a crank-rocker or double rocker system. c) Open configuration for a double crank system. d) crossed configuration for a double crank system

In summary, these 10 basic parameters and other auxiliary parameters used in mechanism calculations are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: Definitions of the base and Auxiliary parameters in a four-bar linkage.

Base Parameters	1	a	x component of the pivot position of the arm selected as the crank
	2	b	y component of the pivot position of the arm selected as the crank
	3	A	x component of the pivot position of the arm selected as the rocker
	4	B	y component of the pivot position of the arm selected as the rocker

	5	k	Length of the link selected as the crank
	6	K	Length of the link selected as the rocker
	7	c	Length of the coupler link
	8	m	x component of the coupler position (CP) with respect to coupler coordinate system
	9	n	y component of the coupler position (CP) with respect to coupler coordinate system
	10	s	Closure parameter
Auxiliary Parameters	11	d	Distance from the end of the crank to the CP
	12	D	Distance from the end of the rocker to the CP
	13	g	Length of the ground link
	14	q	Direction angle of vector d with respect to the ground link
	15	Q	Direction angle of vector D with respect to the ground link
	16	U	Direction angle of the ground with respect to +x
	17	P	Direction angle from d to D
Additional Parameters	18	t	Directed crank angle from g to k
	19	f	Direction angle of the crack (k) with respect to +x
	20	F	Direction angle of the rocker (K) with respect to +x
	21	δ	Direction angle of d with respect to +x
	22	Δ	Direction angle of D with respect to +x

As illustrated in Fig. 1b, the angles between the links and the horizontal axis are defined as functions of the crank angle t (see Fig. 1a). Using these angles, the coordinates of the coupler point (CP) can be derived analytically. The following equation shows that the position of the CP may be expressed in two equivalent forms. The problem now is how these angles depend on t .

$$\begin{aligned} x(t) &= a + k \cos(f(t)) + d \cos(\delta(t)) = A + K \cos(F(t)) + d \cos(\Delta(t)), \\ y(t) &= b + k \sin(f(t)) + d \sin(\delta(t)) = B + K \sin(F(t)) + d \sin(\Delta(t)), \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

2.3 Finding Mechanism Angles

The non-directional expression of the angles S , L and H is found from Fig.4 by the cosine theorem as follows.

$$\begin{aligned} S &= \arccos \frac{K^2 + h^2 - c^2}{2Kh}, & L &= \arccos \frac{c^2 + h^2 - K^2}{2ch}, & H &= \text{sign}(\sin(t)) \arccos \frac{g - k \cos t}{h}, \\ h &= \sqrt{k^2 + g^2 - 2gk \cos t} \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

T and G angles are the rocker and coupler angles required for the mechanism. For a Grashof Mechanism, their expressions according to the configurations in Fig.4 (i.e. according to the angle directions) are as follows.

$$T = \pi - s \cdot S - H = \pi - s \cdot \arccos \frac{K^2 + k^2 + g^2 - 2gk \cos t - c^2}{2K\sqrt{k^2 + g^2 - 2gk \cos t}} - \text{sign}(\sin(t)) \arccos \frac{g - k \cos t}{\sqrt{k^2 + g^2 - 2gk \cos t}} \quad (3)$$

$$G = s \cdot L - H = s \cdot \arccos \frac{c^2 + k^2 + g^2 - 2gk \cos t - K^2}{2c\sqrt{k^2 + g^2 - 2gk \cos t}} - \text{sign}(\sin(t)) \arccos \frac{g - k \cos t}{\sqrt{k^2 + g^2 - 2gk \cos t}} \quad (4)$$

For a non-Grashof Mechanism, the parameter s becomes $s = \text{sign}(\sin t)$ because two closures are visited by the two fixed arms.

Fig.4: a) Open configuration ($s=+1$) and **b)** crossed configuration ($s=-1$) of a linkage. When moving from the open configuration to the cross configuration, the direction of the S and L angles changes to negative.

After finding the rocker and coupler angles (T and G), the directional angles of the mechanism arms with $+x$ are found with Fig.1b as follows

$$f = t + U, \quad (5)$$

$$F = T + U, \quad (6)$$

$$\delta = G + U + q. \quad (7)$$

$$\Delta = \delta + Q - q. \quad (8)$$

After finding the angles in Fig.1b with Eq.5-8, the position of the CP can be expressed by the crank angle with Eq.1.

3 Calculations and Simulation for Cognate Mechanisms

3.1 Naming and Orienting the Parameters of Cognate Mechanisms

Figure 5 is constructed according to the Roberts–Chebyshev method and serves as the basis for determining the parameters of the cognate mechanisms. The parameters in Fig. 5 are named following the convention introduced in Section 2.1. Starting from the k arm and proceeding to the K arm of the reference mechanism, the second and third cognates (Cognate-2 and Cognate-3) are defined, respectively. The K_2 arm of Cognate-2 is chosen to coincide with the K_1 arm of Cognate-1, while the k_3 arm of Cognate-3 is aligned with the k_1 arm of Cognate-1. The vector orientations are consistent with those described in Section 2.1. Consequently, the reference mechanism is denoted by the subscript 1, and the naming and routing rules illustrated in Fig. 3 are applied.

According to Fig. 5, the following cases hold [3, 31]:

Case 1: If Cognate-1 is a crank–rocker (CR), then Cognate-2 is also CR, while Cognate-3 is rocker–rocker (RR).

Case 2: If Cognate-1 is crank–crank (CC), then both Cognate-2 and Cognate-3 are CC.

Case 3: If Cognate-1 is RR, then both Cognate-2 and Cognate-3 are CR.

Fig.5: Drawing of cognate mechanisms for a four-bar mechanism (Roberts-Chebyshev Construction).

3.2 Calculating the Parameters of Cognate Mechanisms of a Given Mechanism

When the fundamental parameters of a reference mechanism (Cognate-1) are known, its auxiliary parameters, such as $d_1, D_1, g_1, q_1, Q_1, U_1$, and P_1 , can be derived using standard trigonometric relationships, as detailed in the second column of Table 2. The lengths K_2, D_2, k_3 , and d_3 can also be calculated directly by analyzing the parallelograms depicted in Figure 4. Because the four triangles in Figure 5 are similar, the remaining side lengths can be determined using similar-triangle relations. When establishing angle equalities, it is crucial to adhere to the specified orientation rules. For instance, while the angles q_1 and q_3 have the same magnitude, their signs are opposite because the q angle is directed from point c to point d ; therefore, $q_3 = -q_1$. All other quantities for Cognate-2 and Cognate-3, as shown in Figure 5, can be similarly expressed in terms of the quantities of Cognate-1 and are provided in Table 2.

Figure 5 can serve as a reference for determining the closure parameters. For mechanisms containing a rocker, the system will have either a rocker-rocker (RR) or crank-rocker (CR) configuration. In a Grashof system, the sign of the rocker angle remains constant. As shown in Figure 5, the signs are positive, negative, and positive, respectively; thus, for a mechanism with a rocker, $s_1 = -s_2 = s_3$. If the mechanism is of the crank-crank (CC) type, the signs follow a different sequence when the output links are held at zero degrees: $s_1 = -s_2 = -s_3$.

Table 2: Cognate formulas for Crank-Rocker (CR) or Double Crank (CC). If the given mechanism is of the RR type, only Cognate-2 remains unchanged. The only difference between Table 2 and Table 3 is that in this case, only s_3 changes.

	Ref.	Cognate-1	Cognate-2
a	a_1	$a_2 = a_1 + g_1 \frac{d_1}{c_1} \cos(U_1 + q_1)$	$a_3 = a_1$
b	b_1	$b_2 = b_1 + g_1 \frac{d_1}{c_1} \sin(U_1 + q_1)$	$b_3 = b_1$
A	A_1	$A_2 = A_1$	$A_3 = a_1 + g_1 \frac{d_1}{c_1} \cos(U_1 + q_1)$
B	B_1	$B_2 = B_1$	$B_3 = b_1 + g_1 \frac{d_1}{c_1} \sin(U_1 + q_1)$
k	k_1	$k_2 = \frac{D_1}{c_1} k_1$	$k_3 = d_1$
K	K_1	$K_2 = D_1$	$K_3 = K_1 \frac{d_1}{c_1}$
c	c_1	$c_2 = K_1 \frac{D_1}{c_1}$	$c_3 = k_1 \frac{d_1}{c_1}$
m	m_1	$m_2 = d_2 \cos q_2$	$m_3 = d_3 \cos q_3$
n	n_1	$n_2 = d_2 \sin q_2$	$n_3 = d_3 \sin q_3$
s	s_1	$s_2 = -s_1$	$s_3 = s_1$ for CR or RR $s_3 = -s_1$ for CC
d	$d_1 = \sqrt{m_1^2 + n_1^2}$	$d_2 = K_1 \frac{d_1}{c_1}$	$d_3 = k_1$
D	$D_1 = \sqrt{c_1^2 + d_1^2 - 2c_1 d_1 \cos q_1}$	$D_2 = K_1$	$D_3 = k_1 \frac{D_1}{c_1}$
g	$g_1 = \sqrt{(a_1 - A_1)^2 + (b_1 - B_1)^2}$	$g_2 = g_1 \frac{D_1}{c_1}$	$g_3 = g_1 \frac{d_1}{c_1}$
q	$q_1 = \text{sign}(n_1) \arccos\left(\frac{m_1}{d_1}\right)$	$q_2 = -P_1$	$q_3 = -q_1$
Q	$Q_1 = \text{sign}(n_1) \arccos\left(\frac{m_1 - c_1}{D_1}\right)$	$Q_2 = -Q_1$	$Q_3 = P_1 - 180$
U	$U_1 = \text{sign}(B_1 - b_1) \arccos\left(\frac{A_1 - a_1}{g_1}\right)$	$U_2 = U_1 + Q_1 - 180$	$U_3 = U_1 + q_1$
P	$P_1 = Q_1 - q_1$	$P_2 = -q_1$	$P_3 = Q_1 - 180$

Table 3: Cognate formulas for double-Rocker (RR).

	Ref.	Cognate-1	Cognate-2
a	a_1	$a_2 = A_1$	$a_3 = a_1$
b	b_1	$b_2 = B_1$	$b_3 = b_1$

A	A₁	$A_2 = a_1 + g_1 \frac{d_1}{c_1} \cos(U_1 + q_1)$	$A_3 = a_1 + g_1 \frac{d_1}{c_1} \cos(U_1 + q_1)$
B	B₁	$B_2 = b_1 + g_1 \frac{d_1}{c_1} \sin(U_1 + q_1)$	$B_3 = b_1 + g_1 \frac{d_1}{c_1} \sin(U_1 + q_1)$
k	k₁	$k_2 = D_1$	$k_3 = d_1$
K	K₁	$K_2 = D_1 \frac{k_1}{c_1}$	$K_3 = K_1 \frac{d_1}{c_1}$
c	c₁	$c_2 = K_1 \frac{D_1}{c_1}$	$c_3 = k_1 \frac{d_1}{c_1}$
m	m₁	$m_2 = d_2 \cos q_2$	$m_3 = d_3 \cos q_3$
n	n₁	$n_2 = d_2 \sin q_2$	$n_3 = d_3 \sin q_3$
s	s₁	$s_2 = -s_1$	$s_3 = s_1 *$
d	$d_1 = \sqrt{m_1^2 + n_1^2}$	$d_2 = K_1$	$d_3 = k_1$
D	$D_1 = \sqrt{c_1^2 + d_1^2 - 2c_1d_1 \cos q_1}$	$D_2 = K_1 \frac{d_1}{c_1}$	$D_3 = k_1 \frac{D_1}{c_1}$
g	$g_1 = \sqrt{(a_1 - A_1)^2 + (b_1 - B_1)^2}$	$g_2 = g_1 \frac{D_1}{c_1}$	$g_3 = g_1 \frac{d_1}{c_1}$
q	$q_1 = \text{sign}(n_1) \arccos\left(\frac{m_1}{d_1}\right)$	$q_2 = 180 - Q_1$	$q_3 = -q_1$
Q	$Q_1 = \text{sign}(n_1) \arccos\left(\frac{m_1 - c_1}{D_1}\right)$	$Q_2 = -P_1$	$Q_3 = P_1 - 180$
U	$U_1 = \text{sign}(B_1 - b_1) \arccos\left(\frac{A_1 - a_1}{g_1}\right)$	$U_2 = U_1 + Q_1$	$U_3 = U_1 + q_1$
P	$P_1 = Q_1 - q_1$	$P_2 = q_1$	$P_3 = Q_1 - 180$

To help readers understand the cognate formulas, we've implemented them in a supplementary Excel file, [CognateParameters.xlsx](#) [Data availability section]. When the parameters of the reference mechanism are input into this Excel sheet, the parameters for the other two cognate mechanisms are calculated automatically. The same algorithm has also been implemented as a Desmos simulation. Desmos is a free web-based tool with features that include a graphing calculator, interactive geometry, and simulations. By entering the reference mechanism's parameters into the Desmos simulation, the parameters of the other two cognates are generated, and the motion of all three mechanisms is animated simultaneously. This provides a visual way for users to confirm the consistency of the triple motion and the correctness of the results.

3.3 Finding the Angles of Cognate Bars

To determine the directional angles of the links, one must first reference the angles of the Cognate-1 mechanism as defined in Equations 5-8. The angles for the other two cognate mechanisms can then be derived from Figure 5, which illustrates the Roberts-Chebyshev construction. The parallelograms in Figure 5 are key, as they must maintain equal angles with the horizontal axis. For instance, since link k_1 is parallel to link d_3 , their directional angles, f_1 and δ_3 , must be equal. These and other relations stemming from parallelism are provided in Eq.9. Furthermore, Eq.10 holds true due to the principle of similar triangles.

$$\delta_3 = f_1, \quad f_3 = G_1 + U_1, \quad F_2 = \Delta_1 = G_1 + U_1 + Q_1, \quad (9)$$

$$\Delta_2 = F_1, \quad F_3 = \delta_2 = F_1 - Q_2 + q_2, \quad (10)$$

$$f_2 = \Delta_3 = f_1 - Q_3 + q_3, \quad \delta_2 = G_2 + U_2 + q_2 \quad (11)$$

$$q_2 = Q_1 - \pi, \quad q_3 = -q_1 \quad (12)$$

3.4 Simulation of Cognate Mechanisms

To create a simultaneous simulation of the three cognate mechanisms, the ground angle of the input link of the reference mechanism (t_1) was designated as the independent variable. The angles of all other links were then formulated as functions of t_1 . These angular formulas, along with the dimensions of the links, were implemented in Desmos to generate a dynamic animation driven by the independent variable t_1 .

When the reference mechanism included a crank, the input link was set to complete a full rotation from 0° to 360° . Conversely, if the mechanism lacked a crank, the minimum and maximum values of t_1 were calculated, and the variable was programmed to

oscillate within this specific range. The code used for the simulation is available for viewing in the left panel of the Desmos interface, and the simulation itself ([Cognate-Simulation](https://www.desmos.com/geometry/tapwahqb46)) can be accessed via a provided link (<https://www.desmos.com/geometry/tapwahqb46>).

4 Real Time Interactive Cognate Path Synthesis Method (RICPS)

At the core of the proposed RICPS method for real-time path synthesis lies the idea of fitting the coordinates of target points—through which the coupler point is required to pass—to the General Coupler Curve Equation (GCCE). To achieve this, the full parameter-dependent form of the GCCE is first derived, and a curve-fitting procedure is applied to match the desired points. The detailed implementation and underlying principles of this procedure are presented in the following sections.

4.1 General Coupler Curve Equation (GCCE)

The General Coupler Curve Equation (GCCE) is a sixth-degree polynomial in two variables that characterizes the coupler trajectory of a four-bar mechanism. Such a polynomial function contains sixteen coefficients, as expressed in Eq.13.

$$K_0(x^2 + y^2)^3 + (K_1x + K_2y)(x^2 + y^2)^2 + (K_3x^2 + K_4xy + K_5y^2)(x^2 + y^2) + K_6x^3 + K_7x^2y + K_8xy^2 + K_9y^3 + K_{10}x^2 + K_{11}xy + K_{12}y^2 + K_{13}x + K_{14}y + K_{15} = 0 \quad (13)$$

The coefficients K_0, K_1, \dots, K_{15} are functions of nine fundamental mechanism parameters, and their full analytical expressions are considerably lengthy, as shown in Eq. 14. The detailed formulations of these coefficients can be found in Appendix B of the study by Erbaş and Bayseç [30]. The complete expanded form of the GCCE expressed in terms of the mechanism parameters - corresponding to Eq. 14 - is provided in full in the supplementary file CognatePresentation.pptx, referenced in the “Data Availability” section.

$$G(x, y) = (x^2 + y^2)^3 + (p_1(a, b, A, B, k, K, c, m, n)x + p_2(a, b, A, B, k, K, c, m, n)y)(x^2 + y^2)^2 + (p_3(a, b, A, B, k, K, c, m, n)x^2 + p_4(a, b, A, B, k, K, c, m, n)xy + p_5(a, b, A, B, k, K, c, m, n)y^2)(x^2 + y^2) + p_6(a, b, A, B, k, K, c, m, n)x^3 + p_7(a, b, A, B, k, K, c, m, n)x^2y + p_8(a, b, A, B, k, K, c, m, n)xy^2 + p_9(a, b, A, B, k, K, c, m, n)y^3 + p_{10}(a, b, A, B, k, K, c, m, n)x^2 + p_{11}(a, b, A, B, k, K, c, m, n)xy + p_{12}(a, b, A, B, k, K, c, m, n)y^2 + p_{13}(a, b, A, B, k, K, c, m, n)x + p_{14}(a, b, A, B, k, K, c, m, n)y + p_{15}(a, b, A, B, k, K, c, m, n) = 0 \quad (14)$$

4.2 Curve Fitting Technique

Because Eq. 14 contains nine unknown mechanism parameters, at least nine target points must be specified for the curve-fitting procedure. Once the designer fixes the required precision points, additional auxiliary points with movable positions are introduced to enrich the data set. The Desmos curve-fitting tool then rapidly computes an ideal parameter vector that best matches all selected points; after deriving the corresponding cognates, the tool simulates the motion of the coupler together with the three cognate mechanisms for visual verification.

The curve-fitting tool in Desmos employs the classical least squares estimation framework to determine optimal model parameters. For models that are linear in their parameters, Desmos computes closed-form solutions through matrix algebra, yielding exact parameter estimates in a single deterministic step [32]. In contrast, when the model contains at least one nonlinearly embedded parameter (e.g., $y \sim a b^x$ or $y \sim a * \sin(bx + c)$), closed-form evaluation becomes infeasible, and the software transitions to iterative numerical optimization [33]. The nonlinear solver is based on a variant of the Levenberg–Marquardt algorithm, which combines the stability of gradient descent with the rapid convergence of Newton-like methods [32]. To enhance robustness, Desmos initializes the fitting process with multiple starting guesses and, whenever possible, analytically resolves linear parameters at each iteration using a variable-projection strategy. Additionally, certain nonlinear models are internally reformulated - for example, $a * \sin(bx + c)$ is converted to $u * \cos(bx) + v * \sin(bx)$ - to improve numerical stability and convergence efficiency [32]. While this framework is computationally efficient and pedagogically accessible, users should be aware that the algorithm does not guarantee convergence to a global minimum, and parameter scaling or local minima may influence the resulting fit [33].

4.3 Development of the RICPS Algorithm

In the cognate-simulation page developed in the Desmos environment, more than nine points are defined under the “Points” folder. Among these, a subset—for example, four points—are designated as fixed precision points that the coupler curve must pass through exactly. These fixed points are displayed in black and their positions are locked. The remaining five points are defined as movable, allowing the user to adjust their positions interactively to refine the curve shape as desired.

In this example, a total of nine points are employed: four fixed (black) and five auxiliary (red), as illustrated in Figure 6. The extended polynomial expression $G(x,y)$, corresponding to Eq. 14, is stored under the “LongPolynom” folder with the label $G(Z)$. The nine defined points are grouped under the set Z , as shown in Figure 6. Furthermore, the relationships between the x- and y-components of each Z point ($Z.x$ and $Z.y$) and the fitting parameters (a_f, b_f, A_f, \dots) are specified in the $G(Z)$ function (Eq.15), forming the mathematical foundation for the curve-fitting process.

$$G(Z) = (Z.x^2 + Z.y^2)^3 + ((Z.x^2(A_f^2c_f^2 + 4A_f^2c_fm_f + A_f^2m_f^2 + A_f^2n_f^2 - 4A_fB_fc_fn_f + \dots \quad (15)$$

Fig.6: Precision points through which the coupler point is required to pass are indicated by black crosses and are fixed at positions Po1–Po4. Red circular markers (Po5–Po9) represent auxiliary points that the coupler curve is also fitted to pass through.

In curve fitting, once the points and the governing equation are defined, it is equally important to specify the search ranges for the mechanism parameters. Although the Desmos curve-fitting tool can produce a solution without any guidance, this often leads to inconsistent or physically unrealistic results due to unbounded parameter exploration. Therefore, the fitting process must be constrained by defining reasonable parameter intervals.

$$I_1 = \{1 \leq k_f \leq 10\} \{1 \leq K_f \leq 10\} \{1 \leq c_f \leq 10\}$$

$$I_2 = \{-2 \leq a_f \leq 2\} \{-2 \leq b_f \leq 2\} \{-2 \leq A_f \leq 12\}$$

$$I_3 = \{-3 \leq B_f \leq 3\} \{-1 \leq m_f \leq 7\} \{-2 \leq n_f \leq 5\}$$

$$I_4 = \left\{ 2 \min\left(\sqrt{(A_f - a_f)^2 + (B_f - b_f)^2}, c_f, k_f, K_f\right) + 2 \max\left(\sqrt{(A_f - a_f)^2 + (B_f - b_f)^2}, c_f, k_f, K_f\right) - \left(\sqrt{(A_f - a_f)^2 + (B_f - b_f)^2} + c_f + k_f + K_f\right) > 0 \right\}$$

$$I_5 = \left\{ 2 \min\left(\sqrt{(A_f - a_f)^2 + (B_f - b_f)^2}, c_f, k_f, K_f\right) + 2 \max\left(\sqrt{(A_f - a_f)^2 + (B_f - b_f)^2}, c_f, k_f, K_f\right) - \left(\sqrt{(A_f - a_f)^2 + (B_f - b_f)^2} + c_f + k_f + K_f\right) < 0 \right\}$$

Fig.7: Parameter intervals selected for generating the corresponding coupler curve. Conditions I1-I3 define the ranges in which the parameters will be searched. Conditions I4 and I5 force the mechanism to be a non-Grashof or Grashof type mechanism, respectively.

As illustrated in Figure 7, these intervals are denoted as I1, I2 and I3. In addition, two optional constraints, I4 and I5, can be introduced to enforce specific mechanism types. The I4 condition constrains the synthesis to a non-Grashof configuration (Fig. 8a), while I5 enforces a Grashof-type mechanism (Fig. 8b). If neither I4 nor I5 is imposed, the curve-fitting procedure identifies the optimal mechanism parameters irrespective of the Grashof condition (Fig. 8c).

Fig.8: Determination of the Grashof or non-Grashof type of the target mechanism. **a)** When the constraint I4 is included in the curve-fitting script, the algorithm is forced to identify a non-Grashof mechanism. **b)** When the I5 condition is applied, the curve-fit procedure is constrained to yield a Grashof-type mechanism. **c)** When only I1, I2, and I3 are defined—without I4 or I5—the curve-fitting process autonomously determines the optimal mechanism configuration, whether Grashof or non-Grashof.

Once the desired curve fit is obtained, selecting the checkboxes labeled Links-1 (black), Links-2 (blue), and Links-3 (red) makes the three cognate mechanisms visible. When the play button next to t_0 is activated, the triplet mechanism begins its motion (Fig. 9). The optimized mechanism parameters are simultaneously displayed in the table at the top of the interface. Fig. 9 illustrates the motion corresponding to the configuration identified in Fig. 8(b). Since the synthesized mechanism is of the Grashof type, it operates in two distinct configurations. The trajectory for the configuration with $sf=-1$ is plotted in green, while entering $sf=1$ allows the user to visualize the motion in the alternate configuration.

Fig. 9. Visualization of the curve-fit result corresponding to Fig. 8(b). The parameters of the three synthesized cognate mechanisms are listed in the table. Because the mechanism is of the Grashof type, it can operate in two distinct configurations. The trajectory shown in green corresponds to the configuration with $sf=-1$. When the closure parameter is changed to $sf=1$, the motion of the alternative configuration can be observed. (<https://www.desmos.com/geometry/rsde7uslgn>)

- 1.) Identify the points where you want the coupling curve to pass.
- 2.) Identify the auxiliary points.
- 3.) Define the parameter intervals.
- 4.) Select Grashof/non-Grashof/free.
- 5.) Evaluate the coupling curve found by Curve-fit.

Fig.10: Flowchart for using the RICPS method.

The procedure described above is summarized in the flowchart presented in Fig. 10. During the synthesis process, the designer can iteratively adjust the positions of the auxiliary points and the parameter ranges until a mechanism that passes through the specified target points is obtained. Although the present example uses nine points, the Z set can be expanded to include additional points, thereby increasing the precision and flexibility of the synthesis. Several representative examples are illustrated in Fig. 11, while further demonstrations can be found in the CognatePresentation.pptx file provided in the Data Availability section.

Fig.11: a) An RICPS trial designed to achieve linear motion (<https://www.desmos.com/geometry/s5zuacg08a>). **b)** A trial designed to draw a circular arc (<https://www.desmos.com/geometry/6eg7jfd0cj>). **c)** Another trial for linear path tracking (<https://www.desmos.com/geometry/zlzlzuoeecz>).

4.4 Mechanism Feasibility and Selection Criteria

Due to the nonlinear structure of the parameter-dependent General Coupler Curve Equation (GCCE) and the admissible parameter intervals used during curve fitting, multiple mechanism configurations may satisfy the same set of prescribed precision points. The objective of the proposed RICPS framework is to generate such admissible mechanism families rather than enforce a single optimal solution.

To provide a systematic basis for selecting among multiple valid mechanisms, objective kinematic feasibility criteria are considered. These include:

1. *Transmission angle quality:* Mechanisms are evaluated based on the minimum transmission angle over the motion cycle, avoiding configurations with poor force transmission characteristics.
2. *Grashof classification:* The satisfaction (or intentional violation) of the Grashof condition is explicitly considered depending on whether continuous crank rotation is required.
3. *Link proportion constraints:* Extreme link-length ratios that may lead to impractical or mechanically unstable designs are filtered.
4. *Continuous drivability:* For mechanisms intended to operate with a continuously rotating input, the feasibility of full rotation is verified.

These criteria do not impose a unique solution but provide a structured evaluation framework that enables designers to rank and filter multiple admissible mechanisms according to specific application requirements. In this manner, solution generation and solution evaluation are explicitly distinguished within the RICPS methodology.

In addition, the instantaneous kinematic quantities (including transmission angle, curvature, velocity, acceleration, and curvature derivatives) can be monitored throughout the motion cycle using the closure-parameter-based kinematic formulation. These quantities provide further objective indicators for evaluating mechanism performance beyond geometric curve matching. Detailed real-time kinematic analysis ([Kinematic Analysis simulation: https://www.desmos.com/calculator/gugnuxjv4i](https://www.desmos.com/calculator/gugnuxjv4i)) capabilities based on the same formulation are presented in [30].

5 Results and Discussion

This section presents and discusses the outcomes obtained using the equations and methods proposed in this study. The performance of the curve-fitting approach is evaluated after analyzing the simulation results and the spreadsheet model constructed from the equations of the derived algorithm. To support these evaluations, several types and configurations of four-bar mechanisms were examined. Their detailed specifications are provided in Table 4.

Table 4: Properties and parameters of the reference mechanisms used in our study. The ten-element parameter list is written in the order $P_r=[a,b,A,B,k,K,c,m,n,s]$. Since the last parameter "s" is not needed in Non-Grashof mechanisms, they can be expressed with nine parameters.

Name	Type	Parameter set
Mech-1	Grashof: Crank – Rocker	$P_r=[-2,2,4,6,6,10,10,4,2,1]$
Mech-2	Grashof: Crank – Crank	$P_r=[0,0,2.7,0,3.5,4.5,5,1,-2,-1]$
Mech-3	Grashof: Rocker – Rocker	$P_r=[3,-1,-1.3,-2.2,5,3.7,3,3,-2,1]$
Mech-4	Non-Grashof: Pi Rocker – Pi Rocker	$P_r=[4.33,2.5,0,0,5,7,5,1,-2]$
Mech-5	Non-Grashof: Pi Rocker – 0 Rocker	$P_r=[0,0,10,0,10,10,14,6.0622,3.5]$
Mech-6	Non-Grashof: 0 Rocker – Pi Rocker	$P_r=[0,0,12,0,5,7,5,2,1]$
Mech-7	Grashof: Crank – Rocker	$P_r=[0,0,4,0,2,5,5,10,0,1]$
Mech-8	Grashof: Crank – Rocker	$P_r=[0,0,6,0,3.5,4.5,5,1,-2,1]$
Mech-9	Non-Grashof: 0 Rocker – Pi Rocker	$P_r=[0,0,8.8,0,3.5,4.5,3.1,2.5,5.2]$
Mech-10	Grashof: Crank – Rocker	$P_r=[-0.2,0,0.2,-0.2,0.15,0.35,0.4,0.1,0.15,1]$
Mech-11	Non-Grashof: Pi Rocker – Zero Rocker	$P_r=[0,0,0.25,0,0.2,0.2,0.3,0.1,0,1]$
Mech-12	Non-Grashof: Pi Rocker – 0 Rocker	$P_r=[10,0,0,0,10,10,14,6.062,-3.5]$

5.1 Testing the Accuracy of the Cognate Algorithm and Simulation

The parameters of each reference mechanism listed in Table 4 were entered as P_r into the Desmos simulation [CognateSimulation-V1](#) (Fig. 12). The simulation computes the parameters of the two corresponding cognate mechanisms, denoted as M_2 and M_3 , using the equations provided in Tables 2 and 3. Subsequently, by performing the calculations described in Eqs. (1)–(10), it generates the simultaneous motion of all three mechanisms. The consistency and realism of the resulting motion serve as indicators of possible numerical or modeling errors in the simulation. To evaluate this consistency, four complementary validation methods were employed.

1. Instantaneous calculation of the lengths of the mechanism arms.

When the positions of the pivot points are calculated instantaneously for each crank angle t , the corresponding distances between these points yield the instantaneous lengths of the mechanism links. For example, the distance between the pivot point (a_1, b_1) and the crank end point $(a_1 + k_1 \cos f_1, b_1 + k_1 \sin f_1)$ represents the length of the crank arm. Although the angle f_1 varies with time, the distance between these two points must remain constant. Any variation would indicate that the crank arm is lengthening or shortening during motion.

These instantaneous link lengths are displayed in Fig. 12 as $L_{length1}$, $L_{length2}$, and $L_{length3}$. The constancy of these values during the simulation confirms that the link lengths remain unchanged throughout the motion. In contrast, introducing even a minor error into the equations in Desmos causes noticeable fluctuations in the computed lengths. When all equations are implemented correctly, the three lengths stabilize immediately. All mechanisms listed in Table 4 successfully passed this verification test.

2. Comparison with handmade mechanisms.

Two manually fabricated four-bar models were constructed for experimental validation—one satisfying the Grashof condition and the other representing a non-Grashof configuration. Based on the simulation results of Mech-1 and Mech-12, the dimensions of all their corresponding cognate mechanisms were determined. Using these dimensions, physical models were built from rigid plastic links cut to scale. The experimental setups and the simulated coupler curves are shown in Figs. 13 and 14. Videos of the handmade experiments here can be viewed in the CognatePresentation.pptx file [Data Availability].

When each cognate model was actuated through one complete rotation of the crank, its motion was observed to match the simulated behavior closely. Furthermore, the coupler curves traced in pencil by the physical models coincided remarkably well with those

generated in the simulation. Additionally, videos of this experiment can be viewed in the presentation file under the heading “hand-made verification.”

Fig.12: A snapshot from Mech-1. M_1 gives the parameters of the reference mechanism. M_2 and M_3 correspond to the parameters of two cognates. L_{eng1} , L_{eng2} , and L_{eng3} show the instantaneous lengths of the arms of each cognate.

Fig.13: Evaluation of Mech-1. **a)** Reference mechanism (M_1) and its coupler curve in black. **b)** Second cognate (M_2) and its coupler curve in blue. **c)** Third cognate and its coupler curve in red. **d)** All cognates of Mech-1. **e)** All cognates and coinciding simulation view

Fig.14: Evaluation of Mech-12. **a)** Reference mechanism (M_1) and its coupler curve in black. **b)** Second cognate (M_2) and its coupler curve in blue. **c)** Third cognate and its coupler curve in red (M_3).

To quantitatively support the visual comparison presented for Mech-12, the experimentally obtained coupler trajectory was digitized from a high-resolution photograph of the hand-made mechanism. The simulated trajectory was then aligned to the experimental image using a two-point registration procedure to determine the exact scale, rotation, and translation parameters.

Following alignment, the deviation between the experimental and simulated curves was evaluated using a nearest-point Euclidean distance metric. For each sampled point on the simulated trajectory, the minimum distance to the digitized experimental curve was computed. After excluding background artifacts, the root-mean-square (RMS) deviation was found to be 18.85 pixels. When normalized by the image diagonal length, this corresponds to approximately 0.6%.

Considering manufacturing tolerances, drawing thickness, joint clearance, and photographic discretization effects, this level of deviation indicates strong agreement between the simulated and experimentally obtained trajectories.

3. Comparison with other studies in literature.

Wu et al. [34] derived the parameters of three cognate mechanisms by applying the General Coupler Curve Equation to a coupler curve with known polynomial coefficients. They reported these parameters in Tables 2 and 4 of their study and presented mechanism snapshots in Figs. 3–5. The configuration listed as Case 1 in Table 2 of Ref. [34] is analyzed in our work as Mech-10. Snapshots of Mech-10 are provided in Figs. 15 and 16, showing excellent agreement with the coupler curves and mechanism positions reported in Figs. 3–4 of Ref. [34]. Likewise, the configuration identified as Case 2 in Table 4 of Ref. [34] is examined here as Mech-11, with a simulation snapshot of its cognates shown in Fig. 17.

Fig.15: Simulation images of Mech-10's cognates at the positions given in Fig.3 of Ref.34

Fig.16: Simulation images of Mech-10's cognates at the positions given in Fig.4 of Ref.34

Fig.17: Simulation images of Mech-11's cognates at the positions given in Fig.5 of Ref.34

5.2 Evaluation of Real-Time Interactive Cognate Path Synthesis (RICPS) Method

The curve-fitting approach adopted in this study also simplifies the classical four-point path synthesis problem. One key advantage is that it can instantly generate descendants of the coupler curve passing through a prescribed set of four points. However, the abundance of possible solutions and the strong sensitivity to point placement and parameter ranges must be regarded as disadvantages.

The RICPS implementation achieved sub-second synthesis times on a standard desktop computer (*Intel i5, 3.20 GHz, Chrome*). By comparison, reported runtimes for algebraic-elimination approaches range from approximately 120 s to 3500 s [35], while metaheuristic optimizers typically require several seconds to minutes [11]. Analytical formulations, such as those proposed by Bai and Angeles [4], are faster but problem-specific. Thus, RICPS offers a one- to three-order-of-magnitude improvement in computational speed while preserving both general applicability and interactive usability.

5.3 Discussion

The accuracy of the cognate algorithms and the simulations and programs prepared with these algorithms have been tested many times. Therefore, the authors have no doubts about this. However, there are advantages and disadvantages to path synthesis with curve-fit and these will be discussed in this section.

Advantages of curve-fit simulation

1. It can be done with easily accessible and free curve-fit programs.
2. It produces fast solutions by responding instantly to the change of the location of the points.
3. Provides different alternatives by presenting the most suitable mechanism for the given target points as well as two cognate mechanisms.
4. The accuracy of the presented solution can be monitored instantly by running the simulation.
5. It is open to generate different alternatives. For example, increasing or decreasing the number of points or changing the weight of the points.

Disadvantages of curve-fit simulation

1. It requires patience and experience to find a suitable solution because of the sensitive dependence on point placements.

2. Since the closure parameter does not appear in Eq.15, Grashof mechanisms cannot distinguish between crossed and convex inclusions. It may happen that some of the target points remain in the open configuration and some in the cross configuration.
3. Since there may be many alternatives of curves that pass very well through the target points, it may be cumbersome to choose a suitable one.

6 Conclusions

The accuracy of the closed-form equations derived for cognate mechanisms was validated using a custom simulation program (*CognateSimulation*) developed from these formulations. Twelve representative four-bar linkages with varying geometric characteristics were analyzed. For the physically constructed mechanism (Mech-12), quantitative comparison between the digitized experimental trajectory and the simulated curve yielded a normalized RMS deviation of approximately 0.6% of the image diagonal. This level of deviation, which reflects manufacturing tolerances, drawing thickness, and photographic discretization effects, confirms the strong consistency between the analytical model and the experimental realization. Furthermore, comparisons with benchmark mechanisms reported in the literature demonstrated consistent kinematic behavior. These validations confirm that the proposed equations provide a reliable and reproducible method for determining the parameters of cognate mechanisms.

A Grashof four-bar linkage, when represented by nine parameters, admits two distinct configurations—convex and crossed—that cannot be interchanged during motion. To capture this distinction, an additional closure parameter must be introduced, leading to a ten-parameter representation. By contrast, non-Grashof linkages can be fully described using the conventional nine parameters. Because the General Coupler Curve Equation (GCCE) does not include the closure parameter, it cannot distinguish between the two configurations; consequently, in Grashof linkages, only part of the coupler curve corresponds to each configuration.

The findings of this study indicate that the GCCE formulation provides limited efficiency for synthesizing Grashof linkages but performs adequately for non-Grashof cases. Future work should therefore focus on developing parametric synthesis formulations that more accurately represent Grashof linkages and enable configuration-dependent path generation.

Data availability: The supplementary materials supporting this study are publicly available on Zenodo at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17332828>. These include (i) an Excel worksheet containing the mechanism parameters and GCCE computation steps, and (ii) a PowerPoint presentation summarizing the simulation results and comparative visualizations of the three cognate mechanisms.

Declaration of generative AI: During the preparation of this work, the authors used ChatGPT for language editing and improving the readability of the text. After using this tool, the author reviewed and edited the content as needed and takes full responsibility for the content of the publication.

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